

Plasmon assisted generation of solvated electrons from low work function scandium oxide and their utilization for enhanced nitrogen reduction

Vera Shilenko^a, Elena Miliutina^{a,b}, Stanislav Cichon^c, Jan Lancok^c, Mariia Erzina^a, Vasili Burtsev^a, Vladislav Buravets^a, Anna Zabelina^a, David Mares^d, Bohuslav Rezek^d, Jaroslav Kulicek^d, Jaromir Vinklerek^e, Sergii Chertopalov^c, Zdenka Kolská^b, Vaclav Svorcik^a, Oleksiy Lyutakov^{a,*}

^a Department of Solid State Engineering, University of Chemistry and Technology, Technická 5, Prague 16628, Czech Republic

^b Faculty of Science, J. E. Purkyně University, Pasteurova 3544/1, Ústí nad Labem 400 96, Czech Republic

^c Institute of Physics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Na Slovance 1999/2, Prague 18221, Czech Republic

^d Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Czech Technical University, Technická 2, Prague 16627, Czech Republic

^e Department of General and Inorganic Chemistry, Faculty of Chemical Technology, University of Pardubice, Studentská 573, Pardubice 532 10, Czech Republic

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ABSTRACT

Solvated or hydrated electrons represent smallest possible anion, which can exist. Due to enormous redox activity these electrons, entrapped in solvent cage, have enormous potential in the field of chemical transformation. However, wide utilization of hydrated electrons is significantly restricted by the methods of their creation, which are either highly energy demanding or based on less probable two photons process. In this work, we propose a rationally designed plasmon active nanostructures coated with low work function material for efficient production and utilization of hydrated electrons. In such case, the coupled plasmon active nanostructure can efficiently convert photon energy in the energy of plasmon excited hot electrons. The electrons are subsequently injected in the low work function material (in this case scandium oxide), facilitating their transfer to surrounding electrolyte. Alternatively, the injected electrons can “wait” in the scandium oxide layer for additional plasmon triggering and injecting through two photons process. The creation of hydrated electrons was confirmed by various techniques, including fiber based optical spectroscopy and electronic paramagnetic spectroscopy. The redox potential of hydrated electrons was subsequently demonstrated in nitrogen reduction, where the 28.3 and 38.0 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ NH_3 yield were reached in photo- and photoelectrochemical regimes respectively. Comparison with alternative method and materials, used for NRR performing in “photo-mode” (not based on hydrated electrons utilization) indicate the huge potential of the proposed structure and approach.

1. Introduction

Solvated electrons are smallest possible anions that can exist in nature [1–3]. Despite of “small” size and solvent cage (or water cage) stabilization, solvated electrons are very aggressive species and can efficiently initiate various fundamental chemical reactions, as well as physical and biological processes [4,5]. As few examples, the covalent bond cleavage in DNA, dissociative electron transfer to CCl_4 , dechlorination of selected aliphatic and aromatic chlorides, decomposition of persistent halogenated pollutants, the reduction of ketones and molecular oxygen or carbon dioxide fixation initiated by solvated (or hydrated) electrons can be mentioned [6–12]. In other words, the high

redox activity makes solvated electrons an attractive agent in the field of chemical technology and catalysis. In this regards, previously reported nitrogen reduction by solvated or hydrated electrons (ideally photo-generated ones) seems to be very promising approach, which may decrease high energy demands of the process in the common Haber-Bosch case, and be performed at mild conditions [2,13,14]. However, the full exploitation of the solvated electrons potential is restricted by hardness of their creation (especially in the case of hydrated electrons) and their transfer from solid surface (heterocatalysis case) or from molecule (homogeneous catalysis) to surrounding solvent cages.

Hydrated electrons are conventionally generated by high energy

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: cichon@fzu.cz, lyutakoo@vscht.cz (O. Lyutakov).

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treatment, including pulsed radiolysis, sonolysis or deep UV irradiation [14–19]. However, these processes are extremely equipment and energy demanding, and can be accompanied by the production of undesired radicals [20–22]. Thus, the development of alternative, mild and more facile methods of solvated electrons generation is of increasing importance [23,24]. This challenge is partially solved in the field of homogeneous catalysis, with utilization of light energy [8,25]. Most of the processes are based on two-step photon absorption, by which the organic molecules can absorb sufficient energy and release photo-excited electron in the external environment (commonly – organic solvent) [8,21,26,27]. This approach is favored by the simplicity of solvated electron generation and availability of an input energy source (visible or UV light). On the other hand, this approach is restricted by the cost of the used organic molecules (expensive complexes of Ir and Rh), necessary addition of sacrificial agent and the number of reported reactions. So that, the solvated electrons generated in such a way can find an application in the range of organic transformation, but their wide utilization in the mass-scale processes, such as CO₂ fixation or nitrogen reduction seems to be questionable [24,28].

In the field of heterogeneous catalysis, the illumination of solid materials surface with UV light is commonly used for solvated or hydrated electrons creation. Excellent results in the production of solvated electrons and their subsequent usage in chemical processes were reached on H-terminated diamonds illuminated with 4.4 eV photons [14,29]. However, such approach requires the illumination with high-energy photons and ultraviolet light utilization. Thus, great attention was focused on the development of alternative materials, able to produce solvated or hydrated electrons by illumination with less energetic photons, ideally with the sunlight [12,30]. Among them, the specially designed melon polymer or 2D metal carbides can be mentioned or upconversion quantum dots [2,14,31,32].

Among other processes, the photoemission of electrons from plasmonic metal nanostructures represents a promising alternative for generating solvated electrons [33–37]. In this case, the hot carriers, generated on plasmonic nanoparticles (NPs) via light absorption and plasmon decay, can subsequently be injected in the surrounding solvent or water. The energy of the resulting electron-hole pair, determined by the incoming photon energy, should be enough to compensate the energy gap between Fermi level and the energy of solvated electron (or energy spectrum of solvated or hydrated electrons). Nanoparticles with specific shape or composition, able to absorb close to UV light, have been reported for hydrated electron photo-generation. In particular, small CuNPs, silver nanoparticles and Al nanocrystals were used for plasmon-assisted generation of hydrated electrons [33,34,37]. However, in these works the utilization of visible light remains still unsolved challenge, despite the direct observation of the increase of solvated electrons yield by the introduction of coupled plasmonic modes or plasmon-active surface roughening [33,38]. Also, the overall photo-efficiency of solvated electrons creation was low (near 1 %). The current results show that further research and design of new plasmon active substrates and hybrid materials should be performed to expand the range of useful light wavelengths and to increase the efficiency of solvated/hydrated electron production and in turn the efficiency of related chemical processes.

2. Experimental section

Detailed description of materials used, samples preparation and characterization is given in Supporting information (SI). Briefly, plasmon active Au grating was created by the sputtering of thin (25 nm) Au layer on the patterned polymer grating. Then, separately prepared Ag nanoparticles were added on a grating surface by electrophoretic approach. In the final step, the thin layer of scandium oxide was deposited on the sample surface by RF magnetron sputtering.

For plasmon-assisted generation of hydrated (or solvated electrons) and ammonia production the samples surface was illuminated by light

emitting diodes or simulated sunlight (in nitrogen reduction experiments, the light power on surface was adjusted to be 200 mW/cm², corresponding to 2 Sun). The generation of solvated electrons was checked using a fiber optics (in the water with pH = 7 and pH = 3, obtained by adding H₂SO₄) or EPR measurements (in a water solution of DMPO).

The ammonia production rate was estimated using photometric kit (Ammonium Test, Merck KGaA, Germany). All experiments were performed using H-type cell in photochemical or photoelectrochemical modes always in 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ solution. The samples were used as an working photoelectrode, the slightly oxidized Ir foil electrode as a counter electrode (in the photo-experiments case). In photoelectrochemical experiments the reference electrode (Ag/AgCl) was additionally used. The Na₂SO₄ solution was initially saturated with nitrogen and additional bubbling with nitrogen was applied during all experiments (common duration - 2 h). To avoid possible mistake the nitrogen purification (see Supporting Information) was used and pH control was performed before and after the experiments. The amounts of NH₃ produced was estimated using photo-colorimetric test.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Main experimental concept

Schematic representation of samples preparation and proposed experimental concept is illustrated in Fig. 1. First, the plasmon active Au grating, able to support the excitation of so-called surface plasmon-polariton (SPP) wave was created using the evaporation of thin Au layer on the patterned surface of DVD disk (surface morphology is shown in Fig. S1). The excited SPP manifest itself as an appearance absorption band, located at 780 nm wavelength (Fig. S2). With regard to the energy, required for overcoming the gap between Fermi level in Au and hydrated electron energy, the absorption of the single low energy photon can not be enough to produce hydrated electrons. To overcome this obstacle, Ag nanoparticles with ca 20 nm size were deposited on the Au grating surface (Figs. S3 and S4). They ensure absorption of photons with higher energy (Fig. S5), through the excitation of the so-called localized surface plasmon (LSP). In both cases, SPP and LSP, the excitation of plasmon resonance occurs as a result of collective oscillation of free electrons in a periodic electromagnetic field restricted by external boundary conditions [39–41]. However, in the case of LSP, the boundary conditions are determined by the physical dimensions of nanoparticles, whereas in the case of SPP, they are related to the translational symmetry of the periodic Au grating. Thus, in the case of AgNPs (LSP excitation), the plasmon field is localized near the surface of the nanoparticles and its local energy values reach relatively large values. In the case of Au grating, the plasmon wave travels along the grating and greater homogeneity of the plasmon energy distribution is achieved, but its local values are somewhat smaller. In addition, the Ag nanoparticles on Au grating surface will guarantee the LSP-SPP plasmon coupling, resulting in the pronounced increase of local plasmon energy [42]. As a result, the created structure cover the wide visible light spectrum (Fig. S2 and S5), with absorption band(s) well overlapping with the spectrum of solar light.

In the final step, the samples surface was covered by the low work function (LWF) material. For the value of WF and expected stability in the electrolyte under photochemical conditions (i.e. the closed presence of the electrolyte), the scandium oxide (hereafter designated as ScO_x until the stoichiometry of the deposited oxide was confirmed) was chosen. It was expected that low WF material will facilitate the electron transfer from sample surface to water molecules cage, increasing in this way the efficiency of hydrated electron creation. Moreover, the plasmon-excited hot electrons can be entrapped in ScO_x layer and subsequently injected in the surroundings by additional plasmon triggering, involving two photon process. One photon/plasmon can result in hot electron excitation and injection from plasmon active metal(s) to ScO_x

Fig. 1. (a) - schematic description of samples preparation; (b) – schematic representation of used experimental set-up and proposed approach for solvated electron creation and solely photo-assisted NRR process.

Fig. 2. (a) - SEM-EDX measurements of Au/Ag@Sc₂O₃ sample surface; (b) – AFM measured morphology of Au/Ag@Sc₂O₃ surface; (c) - Raman mapping of Sc₂O₃ distribution (common Sc₂O₃ SERS spectrum is included as insert); (d) - UV-Vis spectrum of Au/Ag@Sc₂O₃ samples, measured for different thickness of scandium oxide.

and another one from ScO_x to water. It should also be noted that hydrated electrons have short lifetime and can disappear in two ways: either return back to sample surface or participate in the chemical reaction (partly in NRR). Electron back-return is prevented by the presence of low WF material, increasing in this way their participation in NRR. The created structures were subsequently used for nitrogen reduction (Fig. 1b), performed in the photo- (or photoelectrochemical) regimes. Experiments were realized in H-type electrochemical cell, separated by activated Nafion membrane. The NRR was proceeds in the close vicinity of working photo-electrode, illuminated (with exception of some particular cases) by simulated sunlight and served as an emitter of hydrated electrons. The residual holes were subsequently transferred to counter electrode, where the second half reaction, (i.e. water oxidation) take place.

3.2. Characterization of the created structure

The characterization of the samples composition and properties are presented in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. First, SEM image confirm the conservation of periodical grating structure, responsible for SPP excitation (Fig. 2a). The presence of AgNPs (and ScO_x) is less visible on SEM image due to a lower resolution, but both Ag and Sc manifest itself as apparent EDX peaks (Fig. S6). The AFM image (Fig. 2b) performed at higher resolution reveal the presence of characteristic surface features after AgNPs deposition, which are not observed on initial Au grating surface (Fig. S7). Such structures should be attributed to AgNPs covered by ScO_x layer. The AFM scans also show that the grating surface is homogeneously covered by AgNPs, without sign of AgNPs agglomeration. The uniform distribution of Ag and ScO_x was further confirmed using the EDX and Raman mapping (Figs. 2a and 2c), where the relatively

Fig. 3. (a) – XRD patterns of Au grating, Au grating with AgNPs and Au@Ag/Sc₂O₃ structure (40 nm thick layer of Sc₂O₃); (b) – survey XPS spectra of Au@Ag structure measured before and after scandium oxide deposition; (c) – surface work function estimated using UPS (measurements were performed at different spots on sample surface); (d) – changes of Au@Ag/Sc₂O₃ work function with an increase of the thickness of deposited Sc₂O₃; (e) – local distribution of plasmon related electric field under the illumination of Au@Ag/Sc₂O₃ structure (different magnification) with 530 nm wavelengths.

homogeneous signal was obtained from microscopic (EDX) and macroscopic (Raman mapping) areas. The composition of scandium oxide can be estimated from the Raman spectrum as Sc_2O_3 [43] (after determination of the structure and stoichiometry of the scandium oxide, it was designated as Sc_2O_3 in next sections). Control XRD measurements of scandium oxide layer deposited on a glass surface reveal the characteristic reflexes, located at $2\theta = 31.8^\circ$ and 45.5° , that can also be attributed to Sc_2O_3 [96–101–0586]) phase (Fig. S8). Finally, the UV-Vis spectrum of $\text{Au@Ag/Sc}_2\text{O}_3$ shows two slightly overlapped absorption bands, located between 450 and 750 nm (the Sc_2O_3 layer, deposited on the fused silica using the same experimental conditions, was transparent in the 350 – 900 nm optical region, Fig. S9). The first absorption band, corresponding to longer wavelengths is attributed to SPP excitation on Au grating surface. From Fig. 2d and Fig. S2 is evident that SPP peak is shifted due to the difference in the dielectric constants of Au grating environment after AgNPs and Sc_2O_3 depositions. The second absorption peak arise from the LSP excitation on AgNPs surface (Fig. 2d vs Fig. S5). The increase of Sc_2O_3 thickness leads to a slight shift of both, LSP and SPP absorption bands. It should also be noted that the general samples absorption perfectly overlap with sunlight spectrum due to the excitation or two coupled plasmonic modes.

The XRD patterns, measured during particular steps of $\text{Au/Ag@Sc}_2\text{O}_3$ structure preparation are presented in Fig. 3a. The dominant reflexes from plasmon-active metal(s) are observed. Those from Ag are less visible due to a small size of AgNPs and signal overlapping with that of Au. However, apparent broadening of reflexes at 38° , 44° , 65° , and 77° 2θ show the presence of additional signal from Ag. The reflexes from Sc_2O_3 are less pronounced, but in the case of higher Sc_2O_3 thickness (Fig. 3a) we observed the characteristic reflex at 31.8° 2θ and less pronounced one at 45.5° 2θ , both corresponding to the formation of Sc_2O_3 (Reference code: 96–101–0586) [44]. In turn, the survey XPS spectra, measured before and after the Sc_2O_3 deposition indicate the presence of Sc as well as oxygen concentration increase, evident even in the case of smaller Sc_2O_3 thickness (Fig. 3b). Simultaneously, suppression of characteristic peaks from Au and Ag was observed. The detailed XPS spectra of Sc and O, indicate that Sc_2O_3 is formed in slightly non-stoichiometric composition, (see Fig. S10), i.e. with oxygen vacancies, visible from the splitting of oxygen-related peak (in particular, the peak at 532 eV indicates the presence of oxygen species adsorbed at oxygen vacancies). The oxygen vacancies can slightly increase the material work function (which is in general undesired) but also provide sites for entrapment of plasmon-excited hot charge carriers. In turn, common electron-hole recombination cannot proceed through oxygen vacancies, as the residual hot holes are transported to the counter electrode and are not injected into the Sc_2O_3 layer. As a result, the lifetime of these energy rich charge carriers can be significantly prolonged facilitating in such way two photons (more precisely – two plasmons) processes in the generation of hydrated electrons.

As was mentioned above, the presence of Sc oxide layer will facilitate the transfer of plasmon-excited charge carriers, increasing in this way the amount of created solvated electrons and the efficiency of chemical process induced by them. The work function of $\text{Au@Ag/Sc}_2\text{O}_3$ samples was estimated using UPS measurements. In particular, after scandium oxide deposition we observed the significant decrease of WF, up to 2.3 ± 0.2 eV (Fig. 3c, averaged value of WF was observed at 7 different spots on a sample surface). Since the WF value can be affected by the interaction with neighboring metal(s) surface we optimized the thickness of created the Sc_2O_3 layer (Fig. 3d). The value of WF, measured on non-coated Au@Ag surface was 4.6 eV, which slightly deviate from the literature data [45,46], probably due to the presence of silver in the “nanostructured form”. The value of WF of thin Sc_2O_3 films (5 nm) was just slightly lower than the Au@Ag one. After increasing of the film thickness up to 12 nm the more pronounced decrease of WF up to 3.3 eV was observed. The increase of Sc_2O_3 thickness results in even more pronounced decrease of surface WF, up to 2.3 eV, corresponding to the previously published results [47]. A further increase in the thickness of

the thin film does not affect the material WF significantly, since the value characteristic for “bulk” material was reached near 20 nm. Taking into account the limited spatial distribution of SPP (or LSP) evanescent wave tail, the thickness of Sc_2O_3 equal to 20 nm was chosen for further experiments. It should be noted that the observed value of WF (2.3 eV) perfectly correlates with the AgNPs-related plasmon absorption range (the LSP band is located in the 2.2–2.8 eV range, overlapping with the WF value). So that the plasmon triggering will be partially sufficient for the electrons to overcome the gap between the Sc_2O_3 surface and vacuum level and hydrated electrons creation. In addition, the presence of low WF material will partially restrict the injected electron return back to the sample surface and increase their usability for NRR process in this way.

We also performed a range of numerical simulation, to visualize the impact of plasmon triggering of Sc_2O_3 layer, as well as significant local increase of electric field intensity in the case of plasmon coupling. In our simulation, we used the AFM and TEM measured grating morphology, known AgNPs size and optical constants of polymer substrate, Au and Ag [48,49]. The dispersion of real and imaginary part of Sc_2O_3 refractive index (Fig. S11) was determined using ellipsometry (with Sc_2O_3 layer deposited on Si substrate). The correctness of the simulation was verified by the coincidence of the experimental and calculated absorption spectra (Fig. S12). Spatial distribution of plasmon energy is presented in Fig. 3e (sample illumination with 530 nm wavelength) and Fig. S13 (sample illumination with alternative wavelengths). As is evident, plasmonic modes are efficiently excited by the illumination with visible wavelengths. The appearance of plasmonic hot spots between AgNPs is also well visible. The hot spots can be directly excited by the light corresponding to direct light absorption by AgNPs or triggered by SPP wave excited on the Au grating. The plasmon coupling can efficiently increase the energy of free electrons, which can be injected in the surrounding electrolyte through the energy levels, provided by Sc_2O_3 . Moreover, plasmonic hot spots, spatially located in Sc_2O_3 thin film, allow the energy pumping of previously excited and entrapped by Sc_2O_3 charge carrier (i.e. via utilization of two-photon processes for hydrated (or solvated) electrons creation). Additionally, the distribution of the plasmon electric field in the direction of the surface normal (Fig. S14) is localized in ca. first 20 nm of Sc_2O_3 , which finding explains the highest efficiency of solvated electrons production using even this thickness of scandium oxide. Apparently, in the case of larger thickness the residual layer of Sc_2O_3 , which is not subjected to plasmon triggering, acts as a barrier, preventing the injection of plasmon-generated hot electrons from photoelectrode surface to surrounding electrolyte.

3.3. Evidence of hydrated electrons and Kelvin probe measurements

In the next step, we confirm directly the presence of hydrated electron. As was reported before [33,50], the presence of hydrated electron in water will results in the appearance of wide absorption band, located in 650–800 nm spectral range. Because of short lifetime of hydrated electrons, the techniques based in the ultrafast optical measurements are commonly used for detection of this absorption band [1]. We propose an alternative concept, with the utilization of simple home-made device presented in Fig. 4a. Optical fibers connected to a wide spectrum light source and detector are used. The part of fiber shell was removed and naked fiber core was placed in the close vicinity of samples ($\text{Au@Ag/Sc}_2\text{O}_3$) surface (in the underwater conditions). The spectral changes of surrounding (i.e. the appearance of solvated electrons absorption band) in our design was read by fiber evanescent wave, which goes beyond the optical core, as is schematically presented in Fig. 4a. The $\text{Au@Ag/Sc}_2\text{O}_3$ surface was illuminated by the external light source, and in the case of solvated electrons production we expected the appearance of corresponding absorption band, measured in the transmitted light.

Obtained UV-Vis absorption spectra registered for different experimental conditions (measurement were performed under illumination at

Fig. 4. Proofs of hydrated (or solvated) electrons generation: (a) - schematic representation of optical fiber-based concept, used for detection of solvated electrons by evanescent wave; (b) - results of fiber optic measurements, indicating the appearance of characteristic absorption band under light illumination of Au@Ag/Sc₂O₃; (c) - EPR spectra, measured after illumination of Au@Ag/Sc₂O₃ sample in the solution of DMPO in water, characteristic peaks, attributed to a solvated electrons presence are designated by asterisks; (d) - two potential ways of DMPO chemical transformation, related to the presence of solvated electrons or hydroxyl radicals; (e) - scanning Kelvin probe results (scan area 3 × 3 mm², z scale normalized to 1) indicating the positive surface photocharging after Au@Ag/Sc₂O₃ illumination by simulated sunlight (e1 in dark vs e2 under illumination) and its conservation after samples repeated interaction with water (e3 and e4).

pH = 7 or under illumination at pH = 3) are presented in Fig. 4b. Taking into account the short lifetime of the hydrated electrons and their restricted diffusion length only smaller part of fiber evanescent wave will interact with these electrons. Thus, we observed just small absorption band (similar results were published recently in [33]). To partially compensate this drawback, we used significantly prolonged time of spectrum collection (the spectrum presented in Fig. 4b is averaged from 10 measurements, with overall duration of 30 min). In the control spectrum, measured without illumination of Au@Ag/Sc₂O₃ surface at the same pH, no absorption band is observed. Similarly, no characteristic absorption band is observed under illumination at lower

pH also, since protons act as an electron scavenger. We also performed a range of control experiments with samples without Sc₂O₃ layer (Fig. S15). In these cases, no characteristic absorption band is formed. So, obtained results confirm our assumption that electrons are emitted from Au@Ag/Sc₂O₃ to surrounding electrolyte and that the presence of Sc₂O₃ is crucial for this process.

In the next step, we proceed to the EPR based measurements of solvated electrons creation. For the identification of solvated electron the DMPO probe molecules dissolved in the water were used [51]. The DMPO probe can undergo chemical transformation, dependent on the presence or absence of solvated electrons (and protons) or as is depicted

in Fig. 4d [51], with the creation of two types of different radicals, which produce different EPR signals. The EPR spectra, measured after the illumination of samples with simulated sunlight immersed in DMPO solution, are presented in Fig. 4c and Fig. S16. The creation of specific radical(s), under the DMPO reaction with proton and injected electrons is apparent after the illumination of Au@Ag/Sc₂O₃ sample (characteristic peaks are designated by asterisks). Moreover, the intensity of characteristic peaks depends strongly on Sc₂O₃ thickness (Fig. S16). So

that the amounts of the created solvated electron is a strong function of the thickness of LWF material, which should be compatible with the size of plasmonic evanescent wave. The peak intensity was highest for 20 nm thickness and significantly lower for 5 or 40 nm ones. Mere illumination of DMPO solution or absence of Sc₂O₃ layer on the Au@Ag result in absence of the characteristic peaks, indicating solvated electrons production. Similar results (332 – 342 mT range) were observed for Sc₂O₃ powder dispersed in the water (Fig. S17), confirming that the observed

Fig. 5. Estimation of ammonia production: (a) – NH₃ yield as a function of applied potential and Sc₂O₃ layer thickness (including 0 potential vs RHE, corresponded to photochemical production mode); (b) – NH₃ production yield in a several consequent cycles (photo-mode); (c) – wavelength dependency of NH₃ production yield; (d) – schematic representation of the proposed mechanism of hydrated electrons generation, including single or two photons processes; (e) – control experiments with the estimation of NH₃ production (photo- or photochemical mode) using different samples composition (in the case of lower production rate, a longer experimental time was used).

signal should be attributed to DMPO. So, EPR experiments confirm the key role of the LWF material and the need for its efficient plasmonic triggering.

We also performed a WF mapping of the Au/Ag@Sc₂O₃ (20 nm thickness of Sc₂O₃) using the scanning Kelvin probe (SKP) technique. The results are shown in Fig. 4e where WF map across the sample is shown in dark and under illumination with solar simulator as well as after repeated exposures to clean deionized water, each exposure for one minute (the color scale is normalized here for direct comparison). In the WF map under solar light illumination (Fig. 4e, (e1) vs. (e2)), the apparent decrease of WF is observed. In this case, the lower WF corresponds to positive surface photo-charging, which can be attributed to residual holes entrapped in the Sc₂O₃ layer. Subsequent repeated Au/Ag@Sc₂O₃ sample interaction with water almost does not affect the surface properties (Fig. 4e(e3) and 4e(e4)). Positive surface photo-charging can be initially expected, since the samples lose some electrons under the illumination, i.e. under plasmon triggering (indeed most of these electrons return back, but some probably react with the surrounding atmosphere). Since the sample surface is not connected to a counter electrode the remaining holes have no opportunity to leave the sample surface (these residual holes are less redox active and cannot be consumed by water, i.e. scandium oxide is less redox active material).

So, based on the results of fiber based fiber-optical spectroscopy, EPR and Kelvin probe measurements we can conclude that the plasmon triggering leads to the ability of the Au/Ag@Sc₂O₃ structure to inject free electrons in the surrounding and creation of hydrated electrons.

3.4. Nitrogen reduction with utilization of hydrated electrons

As is well known, the hydrated electrons are highly reactive species [5]. Moreover, their energy potential allows them to participate in a range of redox processes, including one being hot challenge in modern electrochemistry – nitrogen reduction reaction (NRR) [13,14]. In the next step, we used the created hydrated electrons even for this purpose. The NRR was performed in photo- or photo-electrochemical regimes. The yield of NH₃ was estimated with photocalorimetry kits, using separately prepared calibration curves (Fig. S18). The results, obtained in photochemical or photo-electrochemical modes are presented in Fig. 5a. The experiments were performed using three different thickness of Sc₂O₃ layer. As is evident, even at photochemical mode (without the utilization of external bias, but with the connection of working electrode with redox-active counter electrode, used for proceeding of parallel reaction – water oxidation) we observed the apparent ammonia yield, which is produced with 28.3 μg.h⁻¹.cm⁻² rate. Such value significantly overperform the recently published ones (Table S1). Surprisingly, utilization of external bias (photoelectrochemical regime) does not affect the NH₃ yield significantly – we observed just slight increase of production rate up to -0.2 V bias applied and its significant decrease at -0.3 V (in this case the parallel process – hydrogen evolution start to proceed on the Sc₂O₃ surface). In all cases, the better results obtained with the Sc₂O₃ layer 20 nm thick, are well correlated with previous ones on the efficiency of plasmon triggering and hydrated electrons production. Even in this case the concentration of produced NH₃ increased gradually and linearly (Fig. S19), during the experiment confirming that potential impurities are not the source of ammonia (otherwise the amounts of produced NH₃ should decrease with time). We also performed a stability tests (Fig. 5b) during five cycles of Au/Ag@Sc₂O₃ utilization in photochemical mode, (duration of each cycle was 2 h). Results obtained indicate just slight decrease of ammonia production yield (by ca 5 %) after 10 h. of photoelectrode utilization. The additional stability tests were performed without electrolyte replacement. In this case, the redox activity of the samples was estimated before and after the continuous use for 6 h (we also observed some increase in pH in this case – Fig. S20). In this case, we observed apparent decrease in the ammonia yield (Fig. S21), probably related to partial degradation of electrode material(s). Additional characterization of electrodes surface was

performed after the stability tests. Obtained results indicate the conservation of electrode surface morphology and chemistry after the stability tests performed with electrolyte replacing each 1 h. However, in the case of experiments without electrolyte replacing apparent degradation of electrode surface was observed (Figs. S22 and S23). Based on the obvious morphological changes of samples surface, it can be concluded that such degradation is associated with the loss of polymer stability with an increase in pH. Finally, control measurements indicate the absence of hydrazine in the reaction mixture (Fig. S24), while ¹⁵N labelling experiments (and subsequent nuclear magnetic resonance measurements) confirmed the origin of ammonia from supplied nitrogen, but not from potential impurities (Fig. S25).

The wavelengths dependency of ammonia production with utilization of hydrated electrons is presented in Fig. 5c. Experiments were performed with utilization of several LED sources, which produced an emission peak with ca 20 nm half width (Fig. S26). The light power on the sample surface was adjusted to 200 mW cm⁻² to highlight the reaction energy input, which is an important element from the point of view of applied catalysis. As is evident, the more pronounced impact has an illumination with wavelength, corresponding to a LSP or SPP plasmon absorption bands (530 or 630 nm). In the case of shorter wavelength (450 nm), which just partially overlaps with plasmon band tail the lower NH₃ production yield was observed. However, utilization of even shorter wavelength (375 nm) results in an increase of the amount of produced NH₃. In this case, the solvated electrons can be produced through the direct light absorption in the Sc₂O₃ layer. Under the samples illumination at 730 nm the ammonia production was still observed, but was almost suppressed at 780 nm. The highest ammonia yield was observed under the samples illumination with a simulated sunlight spectrum, which allows the simultaneous involvement of both LSP and SPP triggering for hydrated electrons as well as plasmon coupling and related increase in the number of hot charge carriers production. Under simultaneous sample irradiation with two LEDs, matching the LSP and SPP plasmon absorption bands (maintaining the constant total power on the surface), the production of ammonium was closed to that achieved with simulated sunlight utilization (Fig. S27). This finding additionally highlights the key role of plasmon triggering. Worth paying attention to is the fact, that even for photons with longer wavelengths (630 and 730 nm cases) the ammonia was efficiently produced, despite the fact that the photon energy is clearly not enough to overcome the gap between the electron level in Sc₂O₃ and in hydrated state. We can suppose that in this case two (or multi) photons process probably takes place, where one photon consumption allows hot electron injection/collection in scandium oxide layer and the second photon, also utilized through plasmon excitation, allows the collected electrons to overcome the residual energy gap for hydrated electron creation. Schematically this process is illustrated in Fig. 5d, where the both, single and two-photons are involved for hydrated electrons creation (and subsequent nitrogen reduction). In particular, high energy photons (designated as hv1 or hv4), absorbed by AgNPs or Sc₂O₃, can ensure the direct injection of hot plasmon-excited electrons from the photo-electrode in the electrolyte. In turn, lower energy photons, designated as hv2 or hv3 and absorbed by Au grating, can ensure the two-photons processes.

Next, we perform a range of control experiment, aimed on the distinguishing of the particular materials contribution to hydrated electrons creation and ammonia production (Fig. 5e). First, in the absence of LWF material layer (Au grating and Au@Ag cases), just vanishingly small (near the limit of experimental error) amount of NH₃ is observed. So, in this case the hydrated electrons are not produced. The illumination of Sc₂O₃, deposited on Au grating surface, results in the nitrogen production, but with significantly lower efficiency. This drawback can be partially overcome by the utilization of external bias. The utilization of Sc₂O₃ deposition on AgNPs array (without the neighboring plasmon active grating) also allows us to perform NRR with efficiency better than in Au grating/Sc₂O₃ case, but lower than in Au/Ag@Sc₂O₃ case. Both, Au grating and AgNPs can support plasmon triggering of hydrated

electrons, but the plasmon absorption band of AgNPs is located at a shorter wavelength, providing the more energy to electrons and their more effective injection in the surrounding electrolyte. Finally, the illumination of Sc_2O_3 deposited on non-plasmonic surface (Fig. 5e, right part), does not lead to an apparent yield of NH_3 . So hydrated electrons are probably not produced in this case. Similar results were observed with the utilization of the Sc_2O_3 layer in the electrochemical mode, indicating the insignificant redox activity of Sc_2O_3 itself, so NRR cannot proceed through common mechanisms, based on nitrogen surface adsorption and reduction [52,53]. So, the NRR performance of pristine Sc_2O_3 (i.e. the capability of scandium oxide to entrap and activate dinitrogen molecule, in a common, non solvated electrons based way) is insignificant. Additional control experiments were also performed at lower pH. The obtained results (Fig. S28) indicate complete NRR blocking even at a pH equal to 3. In this case, the hydrated electrons are consumed by protons which process leads to the appearance of simpler, concurrent to NRR reactions. These observations also highlight the role of hydrated electrons.

Generally, results of control experiments, highlights the key role of each material, used in our case: Ag nanoparticles allows the appearance of hot electrons with enough energy for creation of hydrated electrons. The impact of AgNPs can be enhanced by plasmon coupling with neighboring Au grating, which also allows the lower wavelength utilization for the hydrated electrons creation. In turn, Sc_2O_3 layer allows the more efficient injection of electrons in surrounding electrolyte, and serves as an intermediate charge reservoir for two photon processes and probably prevent the electrons returning back to materials surface.

To further check the contribution of two-photon processes, we proposed a technique combining the z-scan and the method proposed in [54] (the schematic representation of used experimental setup is shown in Fig. S29). In this case, we used a coherent laser beam and optical path equipped with a lens, making possible focusing of the laser beam on the sample and changing the size of the light spot. The total number of incoming photons was kept constant. As a result, the spot size and photon densities per unit area were varied. Ammonia production was used as an indicator, which was expected to remain constant (independent of photon density) in the case of solely one-photon processes or change in the case of two-photon processes. Clear increase in the ammonia production rate with increasing photon density was observed, indicating the presence of multiphoton processes in our case (SX4). It should be also noted that our case does not quite correspond to the traditional case of "two-photon processes" in which two photons have to arrive at one absorption center almost simultaneously (indeed the probability of such event is low at used light on surface power). However, we are rather dealing with a step-by-step process in which the first photon can inject a plasmon-excited hot electron into the scandium oxide layer (where the electron remain for some time), and the second photon will lead to further injection of the electron into the surrounding electrolyte (indeed, the probability of such event can be significantly greater than that in the case of "common" two photons absorption event). We also performed a range of experiments with an introduction of the aperture between the sample surface and the light source. In this case, the aperture allows one to change the illuminated surface area, i.e. the number of incoming photons on the surface. The dependence of the ammonia yield on illuminated area (Fig. S30) was found to be linear, which confirms the plasmon nature of NRR photocatalysis (according to the simple experimental route proposed in [54]).

To compare our results with previously published ones we analyzed the several recent papers, describing the solely photoinduced NRR, with a special attention paid on the recent papers or papers that brought a historically new approach to NRR (for example - the use of plasmonics). The comparison results are summarized in Table. S1 [55–87]. As is evident, the initially "slow" rate of ammonia produced was significantly increased during the last years (from units or tens of $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ up to up to hundreds of $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$). The amounts of ammonia produced can be increased by the addition of sacrificial agent (to facilitate the

second half-reaction, proceeding on the counter electrode), which is to a certain extent economically controversial and therefore was not used in our case. Alternatively, the utilization of UV light part of the spectrum also increases the ammonia production rate. We also used Xe lamp with 320 nm cutoff filter, allowing the part of UV light to participate in NRR. It should also be noted that most of the published works utilize the $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ units for the estimation of ammonia production rate. To compare with our results we recalculate the photo-electrode surface to its weight, using the defined thicknesses of Au, Ag and Sc_2O_3 and their known densities. Then, we estimated the ammonia production yield (see Supporting Information for details) and obtain the value equal to $21\text{ mmol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$. The value exceeds the previously published results more than 10 times. This is quite surprising, and at this stage, we can only assume that such efficiency is associated with a very high efficiency of solvated electrons. At the same time, it should be taken into account that our experiments are somewhat different from traditional ones performed in suspension. In our case, the entire surface of the sample is exposed to irradiation, while in suspension only a part of the catalyst particles have a chance to absorb photons. Nevertheless, we can firmly assume that the approach using solvated electrons significantly exceeds the alternative approaches based on the sorption of a nitrogen molecule on the surface of a redox- and photoactive material and its subsequent reduction. Finally, it should be noted that a similar approach could be used with other low-work function materials, instead of scandium oxide. In such a case, the potential candidates should satisfy following demands: support the efficient electron emission to surrounding electrolyte, be stable in the water under applied external bias, be able to entrap the injected hot charge carriers, support quasi two photons absorption and have a band gap not too large for plasmonic triggering. To date, it is quite difficult to find such a suitable combination of properties in the already described materials with a low work function (for example, our first experiments with utilization of LaB_6 were unsuccessful).

4. Conclusion

The coupled Au grating / Ag nanoparticles structure was covered by a layer of LWF material (Sc oxide) for the creation and utilization of solvated electrons. Coupled plasmonic nanostructures allow efficient absorption of the light energy and conversion of the photon energy in the energy of hot electrons. Hot electrons are subsequently injected in the surrounding electrolyte through the assistance of Sc_2O_3 layer with the creation of hydrated electrons. The production of hydrated (or solvated) electrons was confirmed by EPR, optical spectroscopy, and Kelvin probe measurements. We suppose that the creation of hydrated electrons proceed through one- or two photon processes, where Sc_2O_3 layer serves as a charge reservoir in the last case. Created hydrated electrons were subsequently used for NRR, performed in photo- or photo-electrochemical regimes. We observed production of NH_3 , with excellent yield, overperforming the results published so far or at least comparable with the best actually published results. The range of control experiments indicate that the presence of Sc oxide significantly enhances the efficiency of the hydrated electrons creation and ammonia production. Similarly, significant impact was also observed for plasmon coupling, allowing local increase in the plasmon energy and utilization of longer wavelength for NRR. Generally, our approach, based on the rational design of plasmon active structure and utilization of LWF materials, shows a new, alternative and very perspective way for the production of hydrated electrons and their utilization as a strong redox agent in various chemical transformations.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.apcatb.2025.125148](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2025.125148).

Data Availability

<http://zenodo.org/records/14748723>.

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